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D4: SP2 SOP

Report on the development of an SOP for rBC particle mass measurements with an uncertainty determination, based on the exposure of commercial laser incandescent instruments (SP2) to soot generator (eg. miniCAST) generated bulk and mono-size aerosols (range 70 - 400 nm) both with and without SOM coating during a laboratory inter-comparison exercise

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Glossary

APM	Aerosol Particle Mass Analyzer
BC	Black carbon
eBC	Equivalent black carbon
CS	Catalytic stripper
CPMA	Centrifugal particle mass analyzer
DMA	differential mobility analyser
EC	Elemental carbon
LII	Laser-induced incandescence
MAAP	Multi-angle Absorption Photometer
MAC_{BC}	Mass Absorption Cross-section of BC
M_{BC}	Black carbon mass concentration
OC	Organic Carbon
rBC	Refractory black carbon
SP2-D	Single particle soot photometer version D
SP2-XR	Single particle soot photometer - eXtended Range
TOA	Thermal-optical analysis

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1 Summary

The calibration of the instrument is the focus of this document. The SP2 does not measure refractory black carbon mass, but the incandescence signal that carbonaceous matter emits when it is heated to temperatures close to 4000 K, in a process called laser induced incandescence (LII). The LII signal can then be converted into rBC mass for single particles through calibration; i.e., calibration converts the incandescence peak height to rBC mass. For laboratory studies, we propose that calibration of the SP2 is preferably performed by selecting particles by mass using centrifugal particle mass analysers (CPMA) or aerosol particle mass analysers (APM). For laboratory experiments, calibration with soot from the same source as will be used in the experiments is proposed, if applicable. Non-refractory and non-absorbing mass should be removed before mass selection using thermodenuders or catalytic strippers to avoid calibration errors. For ambient studies, two approaches are discussed. First, one could use a standard calibration material with a low batch-to-batch variability, which makes intercomparisons between sites easier. This is often done using a DMA, and only a few calibration materials available on the market have already been characterized sufficiently in the literature. The second approach is to calibrate the SP2 with ambient aerosols, conditioned with a thermodenuder or catalytic stripper (CS) and a CPMA or APM. The choice depends on research goals, e.g., standard aerosol calibration for inter-site comparisons or detailed microphysical property studies of rBC at a single site.

2 Background

Black carbon (BC) is a term used to describe a component of fine particulate matter ($PM_{2.5}$) that strongly absorbs light, particularly in the visible spectrum, and primarily originates from the incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, biofuels, and biomass (Bond et al., 2013). Despite the widespread use of the term BC in climate and air quality research, it does not refer to a uniquely defined chemical species. Instead, the term BC refers to a class of carbonaceous matter found in aerosol particles with a range of properties. In brief, BC is a material that is refractory (to about 4000 K), is insoluble in water, and is composed of graphite-like carbon atoms that are aggregated together to form small spherules. No instrument can determine all the properties that define BC as a material (Petzold et al., 2013).

BC is a climate-relevant short-lived climate forcer that exerts a positive radiative forcing on Earth's radiative balance (Stier et al., 2007). BC has been shown to warm the atmosphere, both in the air and when deposited onto snow and ice (Wiscombe and Warren, 1980b, a). BC is not well defined as an atmospheric constituent, although it has been the focus of atmospheric scientists because of its potential to contribute to global warming in the short term. Atmospheric BC is a key short-lived climate forcer and an important air pollutant with adverse implications for both human health and Earth's radiation budget.

Despite its central role in climate and air quality studies, black carbon does not denote a single, chemically unique substance. Instead, the term has historically developed as an operational definition that depends on the measurement technique employed and the scientific context. Consequently, several related terms are used in the literature, including black carbon (BC), elemental carbon (EC), refractory black carbon (rBC), and soot, each carrying distinct conceptual and methodological implications.

Although this method has certain drawbacks, the mass of BC can be optically defined. In its broadest sense, BC refers to the fraction of atmospheric particulate matter that strongly absorbs light in the visible spectrum. This definition is inherently optical and is closely linked to the direct climate impact of BC. BC is commonly measured using filter-based light absorption instruments, such as aethalometers, multi-angle absorption photometers (MAAP), photoacoustic spectrometers, or photothermal interferometers. These techniques infer BC mass concentrations from the absorption of light by aerosol particles. Because optical methods are sensitive not only to BC mass but also to particle morphology, mixing state, and coating effects, the inferred BC concentrations may vary considerably between instruments and sites (Asmi et al., 2025). In filter-based absorption photometers, the filter material also impacts the instrument's response to light-absorbing and light-scattering aerosols, which must be corrected for. The optically determined mass of BC is termed equivalent BC (eBC) and is an estimate of the amount of BC using a fixed mass absorption cross section (MAC_{BC}) that is fixed (Asmi et al., 2025; Petzold et al., 2013a)

Elemental carbon (EC) is obtained using analytical methods designed to separate carbonaceous aerosol fractions according to volatility and reactivity. Thermal–optical analysis (TOA), widely applied in air quality monitoring networks, sequentially heats a sample under inert and oxidizing atmospheres to volatilize organic carbon (OC) and subsequently oxidizes the more refractory carbon fraction, defined as EC (Birch and Cary, 1996). The distinction between OC and EC is operationally determined, with protocol-dependent temperature thresholds and correction schemes to account for the pyrolysis of organic material. Consequently, reported EC concentrations may differ significantly between protocols (e.g., EUSAAR, IMPROVE, and NIOSH). Although EC and BC are often treated as equivalent, they are not equivalent. EC is defined by its thermal stability, whereas BC is defined by its optical absorption. Nevertheless, EC remains a widely used surrogate for BC, particularly in air quality and health studies, because of its relatively standardized measurement protocols.

Refractory black carbon (rBC) is defined more narrowly as the carbonaceous particle fraction that is sufficiently refractory to remain intact at very high temperatures (≈ 4000 K) when heated by a focused laser beam. This fraction can be detected and quantified at the single-particle level using laser-induced incandescence (LII) techniques, most notably the single-particle soot photometer (SP2). The rBC mass is determined from the intensity of the incandescence signal as individual particles vaporize, providing high specificity and size-resolved information (Stephens et al., 2003). Unlike filter-based optical instruments, SP2 measurements are relatively insensitive to non-BC aerosol components, making rBC a robust metric for quantifying the most refractory fraction of light-absorbing carbon. However, rBC excludes light-absorbing organic compounds (often referred to as “brown carbon”) and may differ in magnitude from BC or EC estimates.

The term soot originates from combustion science and is used to describe fractal-like aggregates of nanometer-scale carbon spherules formed during incomplete combustion. Soot is primarily composed of graphitic carbon layers, often with surface-bound organic or inorganic material, depending on the combustion source and atmospheric processing. Unlike BC, EC, or rBC, soot is not defined by a measurement protocol but rather by morphology and formation process. Characterization typically relies on electron microscopy or Raman spectroscopy to resolve particle structure. In atmospheric science, soot is often treated as synonymous with BC; however, the distinction is useful in combustion and material science contexts, where microstructure and formation pathways are of primary interest.

The diversity of definitions highlights the absence of a single, universally accepted standard for black carbon. Instead, each definition reflects a different perspective: BC emphasizes optical properties and climate relevance; EC emphasizes thermal stability and operational reproducibility; rBC emphasizes refractory properties and single-particle quantification; and soot emphasizes morphology and formation processes.

Although these terms often overlap in practice, the distinctions are not trivial. Reported concentrations of BC can differ by factors of two or more depending on the chosen measurement technique (Pileci et al., 2021; Tinorua et al., 2024). This complicates the intercomparison of datasets and modelling studies, underscoring the importance of explicitly stating the definition and measurement approach used. The harmonization of terminology and improved cross-calibration of methods remain active areas of research, particularly given the role of BC as one of the most potent contributors to anthropogenic radiative forcing after carbon dioxide and methane.

3 Measurement principle of SP2

The SP2 uses a continuous high-power intracavity infrared (IR) laser to heat light-absorbing carbonaceous aerosols to the point of incandescence (Baumgardner, 2004; Schwarz et al., 2006; Stephens et al., 2003). This technique is known as laser-induced incandescence (LII). In SP2, LII is achieved by passing sample aerosol particles through a high-power (~ 1 kW) intra-cavity laser beam (1064 nm in wavelength) and detecting them on a particle-by-particle basis using detectors.

The energy absorbed by particles in the laser beam is converted into heat, which heats the particles. Particulate matter that is refractory enough to heat to temperatures that emit thermal radiation at visible wavelengths (incandescence) is detected by the instrument using optical detectors. We call this the LII signal. The heating of the particles in the laser beam is an optical process, whereas the incandescence signal originates from the

thermal emission of heated matter (Baumgardner, 2004; Schwarz et al., 2006; Stephens et al., 2003). This dependence on the amount of heated matter that emits thermal radiation through incandescence is the reason that the LII technique is a mass-based method (Moteki and Kondo, 2010a, b). The LII signal is proportional to the light-absorbing mass in the particles that is refractory enough to reach such a high temperature. Carbonaceous aerosols that originate from the incomplete combustion of carbon-based fuels have these properties; that is, they survive to temperatures exceeding 4000 K (Moteki and Kondo, 2010a). These carbonaceous particles are black, refractory, and detected by the SP2; hence, the term refractory black carbon (rBC).

The sample aerosol is led through the centre of the beam so that they are exposed to the maximum laser intensity in the beam. As the sample aerosol traverse the laser beam, detectors monitor both the scattering and incandescence signals. All the sampling of the detectors is done simultaneously using a digital oscilloscope. As the particles traverse the laser beam, they can scatter or absorb light which can be detected by the sensors that are focused on the volume where the particles traverse the laser beam.

The beam profile of the laser is adjusted to a TEM00 mode which means that the beam shape is gaussian. The TEM00 mode ensures that the laser power is the maximum achievable at a given setpoint (pump-laser current). A properly set up laser will ensure that the laser power is sufficiently high such that the detection limit of the instrument is as expected (Schwarz et al., 2010). Laser power that is too low will not be able to heat small particles sufficiently for detection.

3.1 SP2-D

Four detectors monitor aerosol particles as they traverse the infrared laser beam. All four detectors have a high gain (HG) and a low gain (LG) channel that are digitally stored by analyzing the particle traces left in a digital oscilloscope sampling all eight channels simultaneously at a sampling rate of 2.5 MHz. For each particle event, a sampling window of 100 data points is stored, which is 40 μ s in length.

Two of the detectors in the instrument are used to detect the LII signal. One broadband channel (BB) and one narrow band channel (NB). The BB wavelength range is 350 – 800 nm, and the NB wavelength range is 610 – 800 nm (Laborde et al., 2012b). The BB detector is the most sensitive to rBC. The NB detector, in combination with the BB detector, is used to determine the temperature at which the particles incandesce. Some users have modified the optical filters of the BB and NB so that the bandpass optical filters do not overlap; this makes the NB detector the blue-band detector and the BB detector the red-band detector, with bandpass filters of 300 – 550 nm and 580–710 nm, respectively.

The remaining two detectors are used to detect the elastically scattered light from the laser beam. The scattered light is detected by the scattering detector and can be used to determine the optical size of the particles and a position-sensitive detector (PSD) to determine the particles' position in the laser beam (Gao et al. 2007). Both the PSD and the scattering detector can be used to calculate the coating thickness of the aerosol particles, i.e. the thickness of the shell surrounding the rBC particle using the leading-edge-only (LEO) technique (Gao et al., 2007).

The design of the SP2-D requires several steps to ensure that the instrument operates optimally. These include ensuring that the laser is in TEM00 mode, which ensures the highest laser power at the lowest pump laser current. Adjusting the laser can move the laser beam location inside the instrument and change the optical alignment of the detectors. The work by (Laborde et al., 2012b) provides a list of steps to ensure proper alignment and (Schwarz et al., 2010) describe how to ensure that the laser is powerful enough.

3.2 SP2-XR

The working principle of the SP2-XR is essentially the same as the SP2-D with a few key differences that makes it more suitable for long term monitoring with an improved optical design compared to the SP2-D. As the name suggests, SP2-XR has a wider range than SP2-D and can detect rBC particles in the size range of

50 to 800 nm (assuming void-free particles with a bulk density of 1.8 g cm^{-3}). The detection of scattering particles is also possible over a wider range compared to SP2-D; 100 – 500 nm for the XR compared to approximately 150–400 for the D model.

The SP2-XR uses the same IR laser to achieve LII as the SP2-D; however, the improved design is more stable, requiring less tuning and alignment prior to deployment than the SP2-D. The SP2-XR does not have a narrowband channel or a split detector. The broadband and scattering detectors are like those of the SP2-D, with the main difference being that the high-gain and low-gain signals are combined online so that the output is combined on the fly.

4 Calibration of SP2

The SP2 instrument response is proportional to the light-absorbing mass of refractory carbonaceous material in the sample aerosol. This has been demonstrated in numerous studies focusing on combustion and carbonaceous aerosols (Laborde et al., 2012a; Moteki and Kondo, 2010a). The peak height of the incandescence signal is the best indicator of the particle mass because when the incandescence signal peaks, no significant mass has yet been lost from the incandescence particle (Moteki and Kondo, 2010a). After the point of maximum incandescence, particles start to vaporize, and the signal degrades in the laser beam; after which the signal strength is no longer representative of the initial mass of the particle. Therefore, calibration should be performed using the incandescence peak height on the broad- and narrow-band detectors. Studies that have investigated the SP2 performance of different types of carbonaceous aerosol particles and calibration materials have used instrumentation that selects particles based on their mass (Laborde et al., 2012a; Moteki and Kondo, 2010b). Therefore, the preferred method for calibrating an SP2 is to select particles by mass. Other calibration methods are discussed later; however, first, we discuss calibration by selecting particle mass.

The mass of refractory black carbon (rBC) reported by the instrument depends on its calibration. The quantity rBC is instrumentally defined as the LII signal peak height as detected by the instrument, which is converted into rBC mass according to the calibration (Petzold et al., 2013). Although the instrument does not measure the mass directly, the LII signal is proportional to the refractory mass that can reach the point of incandescence, which the instrument can detect through its optical detectors as thermal radiation emitted by particles, one particle at a time. This is why calibration is so important for the SP2.

Laser alignment and laser power adjustment have been discussed in literature (Laborde et al., 2012b; Schwarz et al., 2010) and in the operator's manual provided by the manufacturer. Laser power and laser alignment are performed using scattering particles, which are typically polystyrene latex (PSL) particles with a known size (e.g., ~200 or 269 nm). After aligning the optical components, a PSL calibration is required, as the instrument response is likely to have changed. The scattering channel can then be calibrated using a range of different-sized PSL particles, typically in the range of 150 to 350 nm, to obtain a calibration curve for scattering particles. Alternatively, other monodisperse particles can be used for the scattering channel calibration, such as nebulized ammonium sulfate and a DMA, given that the refractive index of the nebulized substance is known. However, it should be noted that a PSL calibration is very easy to set up and provides precise results.

4.1 Mass calibration of the SP2

As the SP2 instrument response is proportional to the mass of rBC in a particle, the preferable choice for SP2 calibration is to select particles according to their mass. This can be accomplished using a centrifugal particle mass analyzer (CPMA) or an aerosol particle mass analyzer (APM) (Ehara et al., 1996; Olfert and Collings, 2005). The CPMA and APM are designed to classify aerosol particles according to their mass-to-charge ratio. This is achieved by balancing two opposing forces acting on a charged particle as it travels through a concentric, cylindrical, and rotating electrode system. An aerosol particle with a given mass-to-charge ratio will experience exactly balanced forces, thereby allowing it to follow a stable trajectory through the device. Particles with mismatched mass-to-charge ratios are displaced and lost to the electrodes. By changing the rotation speed and electric field, the instruments select particles of different masses.

4.1.1 Mass calibrations for lab experiments

When calibrating the SP2 using this method, the user can choose to calibrate the instrument with the aerosol that will be sampled. This is often possible to do in laboratory experiments if the same soot source is used throughout the experiments. Such experiments can be conducted, for example, using a miniCAST or Argonaut burner, or other laboratory soot from flames. It should be noted that the Palas spark-discharge nanoparticle generator is not suitable for calibrating the SP2 (Gysel et al., 2012). Although sometimes referred to as a “soot generator,” this and other spark-discharge devices do not produce highly graphitized soot, as produced by flames, but rather amorphous-carbon aggregates.

When selecting particles by mass using a CPMA or APM, it is crucial to ensure that the particles do not contain non-absorbing mass. This can be achieved using a thermodenuder or a catalytic stripper (CS) to eliminate non-absorbing and non-refractory matter from the particulate phase before selecting the particles according to their mass. The temperature of the CS or thermodenuder should be maintained below 350 °C. Charring of the calibration aerosol particles is not desirable because the amount of charring depends on many factors that cannot be easily controlled and would therefore introduce uncertainties to the calibration.

Instrument	Mean concentration (ug/m ³)	Difference (compared to Tropos SP2-D)
SP2-D Tropos	56.3	0 %
SP2-D FMI	55.7	-1.1 %
SP2-XR	54.5	-3.2 %

Table 1. Intercomparison of two SP2-D and one SP2-XR after calibration with miniCAST soot and CPMA + CS.

Figure 1. Two SP2-D instruments calibrated during the Tropos workshop in October 2023 are shown. The instruments were calibrated using miniCAST soot, which was then passed through a catalytic stripper (CS)

and subsequently mass-selected using a CPMA. Both SP2-D instruments agreed within 1.1 % of each other when comparing the total rBC mass concentrations. The figure presents the mass size distribution as a function of the mass equivalent diameter, assuming a density of 1.8 g cm^{-3} . This agrees with an earlier study looking at inter-comparability between different SP2 which found that BC mass distributions were within $\pm 10\%$ (Laborde et al., 2012b).

4.1.2 Mass calibrations for ambient experiments

The rBC concentrations and mass distributions in ambient air are often the focus of SP2 measurements when not doing dedicated lab experiments. For ambient measurements, rBC aerosols can be more heterogeneous. In laboratory or chamber studies, the soot source can be the same; however, in ambient air, the source of the soot particles is bound to be from a variety of different sources.

There are two calibration approaches. The first involves stripping volatile and semi-volatile aerosol constituents before mass selection by a CPMA or APM using a thermodenuder or a CS. This has been shown to remove the non-absorbing aerosol mass from the particulate phase (Moteki and Kondo, 2010b), and the remaining aerosol has a very low single scattering albedo, indicating that the residual aerosol is refractory carbonaceous matter, at least for the sub-micron aerosol in the size range that the SP2 measures. This approach effectively calibrates the SP2, through mass selection of calibration aerosol particles, to the non-volatile mass that the thermodenuder or CS is unable to remove from the particulate phase. Studies on e.g. the Tokyo aerosol has found good agreement using this method between ambient soot and fresh diesel soot (Moteki and Kondo, 2010b). The second option, which could add an additional degree of inter-comparability between sites with different non-volatile carbonaceous aerosol particles, is to use a dedicated calibration material for the SP2. These calibration materials, their pros and cons, will be discussed in the next section. The most recommended calibration material used for this purpose, is unfortunately not available any more by the supplier so new users are left to choose other calibrations materials if pursuing this alternative. The manufacturer of the SP2 can provide an alternative, and popular, calibration material which has been shown to have a small batch-to-batch variability.

We are cautioned in recommending one approach over the other, as it depends on the nature and aim of the research conducted, as one approach might have an advantage over the other based on the research question at hand. For example, when comparing rBC size distributions across multiple sites, one could favor having a standard aerosol for calibrating the SP2 using a CPMA/APM setup; however, when exploring coating and other optical properties, the thermodenuder/CS CPMA/APM approach at one single site might be preferable if the residual aerosol at the site is known to be substantially different from, for instance, diesel soot or biomass burning aerosols.

Figure 2. Calibration curve for miniCAST soot for SP2-XR compared with the factory calibration in terms of incandescence peak height versus particle mass. The figure shows that the SP2-XR is less sensitive to miniCAST soot than the factory calibration expects for a rBC particle with the same mass.

Figure 2 shows the different instrument responses of an SP2-XR to thermodenuded miniCAST soot. The green line shows the factory calibration of the incandescence peak height on the x-axis versus particle mass on the y-axis. The orange line and blue markers represent the actual mass of the particles selected by a CPMA, where the markers are the data points and the orange line is the curve fit to those data points. The figure illustrates that factory calibration of the SP2-XR would have shown a different rBC size distribution and total rBC mass if the original calibration had been used. The miniCAST soot sample yielded a lower incandescence peak height than the standard Aquadag calibration, which would bias the results from the miniCAST soot experiments low; that is, the miniCAST soot sample yielded a lower signal in the SP2-XR than the Aquadag calibration would lead the operator to believe. In this case, the incandescence peak height was 63% lower than the expected peak height for the size selected by the CPMA.

4.2 Calibrations for ambient experiments with a DMA

CPMA or APM instruments are not always available when deploying an SP2 for field campaigns because they are heavy, bulky, and expensive compared to, for example, a DMA. The use of a DMA for field calibrations is probably the most widely used technique to calibrate SP2s, at least for field campaigns. Furthermore, DMAs are often found at measurement stations in SMPS or DMPS systems, and their correct size selection can be evaluated using PSL spheres before calibrating the SP2 using the same PSL spheres, which are used to calibrate the scattering channels of the SP2.

CPMA or APM selects particles based on their mass-to-charge ratio, whereas a DMA selects particles based on their electrical mobility (Flagan, 1999). The relationship between particle mass and electrical mobility is not trivial and depends on the calibration material used. Because SP2 is sensitive to the rBC particle mass rather than the mobility diameter, the effective density of the calibration material is required to convert differently sized particles with a DMA to particulate mass using an effective density that is size-dependent.

The effective densities of Aquadag new (lot #9627) and Aquadag classic (lot #9054) and FS (Alfa Aesar Inc. lot #40971 batch #FS12S011) have been characterised and parametrised for calibrating the SP2 using a DMA (Gysel et al., 2011; Moteki and Kondo, 2010a). In this way, the DMA selected size can be used to convert the selected monodisperse aerosol particles to their equivalent mass using a size dependent effective density function and thus allow for the SP2 to be calibrated using a DMA. (Laborde et al., 2012b) showed that 300 nm DMA selected Aquadag particles (equivalent to 8.9 fg in mass) compared the best among different instruments,

and (Baumgardner et al., 2012) suggested that this diameter can be used to convert an Aquadag calibration to an FS equivalent (Alfa Aesar Inc. lot #40971 batch #FS12S011) calibration using a correction factor of 0.75.

4.2 Calibration materials

Several different calibration materials have been investigated for calibrating SP2s (Gysel et al., 2012; Laborde et al., 2012a; Moteki and Kondo, 2010a). Their performance has mainly been estimated based on how they perform in comparison with ambient soot or diesel soot, in addition to their batch-to-batch variability. We do not present an exhaustive list of all available calibration materials here but restrict the discussion to the most relevant materials.

The instrument manufacturer supplies SP2 operators with aqueous deflocculated Acheson graphite (Aquadag®) to calibrate their instruments. Aquadag is a well-studied material comprising aggregates of “irregular flakes of graphite” (Moteki et al., 2009). Aquadag been shown to have a small batch-to-batch variability although the SP2 instrument response is not the same as for ambient soot aerosols (Baumgardner et al., 2012; Gysel et al., 2011; Laborde et al., 2012a). The manufacturer distributes Aquadag new (lot #9627) and Aquadag classic (lot #9054). These lots have been shown to be similar to each other in terms of batch-to-batch variability (Laborde et al., 2012a) and the solution concentration does not seem to alter the calibration results (Gysel et al., 2011).

In literature, the fullerene soot that has the closest characteristics to ambient soot and diesel soot is the Alfa Aesar Inc. lot #40971 batch #FS12S011 (Baumgardner et al., 2012; Laborde et al., 2012a; Moteki and Kondo, 2010a). However, this lot and batch are no longer available on the market and cannot therefore be recommended for this purpose because it is not available for purchase. The reason why this batch performed well in comparison with ambient soot, whereas Alfa Aesar Inc. lot #40971 batch #L18U002 did not is unclear.

In addition, Moteki and Kondo (2010) studied other types of calibration materials for the SP2 in addition to Aquadag and FS. These included colloidal graphite (Alfa Aesar Inc., Stock#41773, Lot#C07M13), glassy carbon (Tokai GC-100 nm and Tokai GC-50 nm), Aqua-black (001 and 162 from Tokai Carbon, Japan), and glassy carbon-0.4–12 μm (Alfa Aesar, USA, stock# 38001). Moteki and Kondo (2010) concluded that “At least for ambient soot in Tokyo urban area, the fullerene soot [lot #40971 batch #FS12S011] is the best choice among the eight commercial BC samples tested here, considering the similarities of the physical properties...”.

Moteki and Kondo 2010 further concluded that “For ambient soot measurements, it is necessary to choose a calibration material whose refractive index and particle shape are close to those of ambient soot.”

Figure 3 shows different calibration materials normalized to diesel exhaust from a EURO3 diesel engine to illustrate their different behaviors. Diesel exhaust was first passed through a thermodenuder operating at 350 °C to remove any volatile material from the particulate phase, then passed through a neutralizer, and subsequently through a CPMA for mass selection. The CPMA was used to select particle sizes between 0.1 and 72.4 fg for soot calibration. For each mass setpoint, the LII peak amplitude of the AD distribution was determined. The results are presented as a table of AD values for each mass setpoint. An average thermodenuded diesel sample was fitted with a second-order polynomial function. The values generated using this function for the entire mass point range were then used for calibration and normalization in Fig. 4b-c.

Figure 3a shows how well the thermodenuded diesel exhaust calibration curve matched subsequent measurements of the same diesel exhaust using the same thermodenuder setup. The instrument response to diesel exhaust in terms of LII peak height, as detected by the instrument, should therefore be 1. The remainder of the experiments were compared with this calibration in terms of relative LII peak heights as a function of mass. Figure 3b shows the LII peak heights from thermodenuded ambient aerosol particles in the SP2-XR. Again, the graph shows the LII peak heights in relative terms compared to the thermodenuded diesel exhaust in the mass range of 2 to 30 fg per particle. The ambient and diesel exhaust signals compared well (within 10%) up to approximately 5 fg, after which the ambient rBC aerosol particles started to yield a lower LII peak height than the diesel soot. This behaviour is like what has been reported in literature before (Laborde et al., 2012a).

Figure 3c shows the AD ratios of Aquadag new (lot #9627), Aquadag classic (lot #9054), and FS (Sigma-Aldrich 572497-5G lot MKBB8240). From Figure 3c, it is evident that calibration materials behave differently than diesel soot (Figure 4a) and ambient soot (inferred from Figures 3a and 3b). This highlights the importance of the calibration material used to determine the rBC mass and size distribution in ambient samples. If the same calibration material is used for different SP2s, the results should be intercomparable, provided the SP2s are set up properly and calibrations are performed in a similar manner. However, the calibration aerosol must also be compared with ambient or laboratory-generated soot, depending on the nature of the measurements, to obtain the correct rBC mass or mass distribution.

5 Conclusions

For laboratory research, we suggest calibrating the SP2 by selecting particles based on mass using centrifugal particle mass analyzers (CPMA) or aerosol particle mass analyzers (APM). If feasible, calibration with soot from the same source intended for experiments is recommended. To prevent calibration inaccuracies, non-refractory and non-absorbing mass should be eliminated before mass selection using thermodenuders or catalytic strippers. For ambient studies, two methods are considered. The first involves using a standard calibration material with minimal batch-to-batch variability, facilitating site-to-site comparisons. This is typically achieved with a DMA, and only a few calibration materials on the market have been sufficiently characterized

in literature for this purpose. The second method involves calibrating the SP2 with ambient aerosols, incorporating a thermodenuder or catalytic stripper (CS) and a CPMA or APM. The choice between these methods depends on research objectives, such as standard aerosol calibration for inter-site comparisons or in-depth studies of rBC microphysical properties at a single location.

6 References

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